



Figure S3. Principal Analysis of Components (PCA) of morphology. PC1 explains 19.7% and PC2 explains 15.3% of the variance. HW: head width; HH: head height; HL: head length; TRL: trunk length; INL: interbrachial-nasal length; HUL: humeral length; FAL: forearm length; FL: femur length; TL: tibia length; FTL: hind foot length; TAL: tail length; PG: pelvic girdle; SG: shoulder girdle; SHF: scales of the third finger of hindfoot; SFF: scales of the third finger of forefoot.